

Is Classical Statistical Mechanics Derivable from Time Independent Quantum Mechanics?

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Equilibrium classical statistical mechanical distributions are often derived from maximizing (in a variational way) Shannon's entropy $d(p,x) \ln(d(p,x))$ (where $d(p,x)$ is the density for having a particular momentum at position x (1- dimension) subject to a constraint. It appears to be accepted in the literature that Shannon's entropy is a measure of a lack of information and it is this which one is attempting to maximize. The constraints in a physical system stand in the way of the maximization. Quantum mechanical wavefunctions $W(x)$ on the other hand are solutions of the time independent Schrodinger equation. It has been argued [2], however, that the Fourier series of $W(x) = \sum_p f(p) \sin(px)$ can be used to describe the quantum system in terms of a probability distribution with $f(p) \sin(px)/W(x)$ being the conditional probability to have a momentum p at x . If one attempts to create a wavefunction with a maximum lack of information, one might choose $f(p) = \exp(-ap^2)$ (from the central limit theorem). Such a choice would lead to $W(x) = \exp(-bx^2)$, the ground state of an oscillator. The question is whether this maximization or lack of information in quantum mechanics carries through to the classical statistical mechanical case. We argue that it does because the time independent Schrodinger equation can be written as:

$\ln(d(x)) + V(x) = 0$ for the oscillator case. This resembles the variational result of: $d(x) \ln(d(x)) + bV(x)d(x)$ which is used to derive the spatial part of a classical statistical mechanical problem. One can also apply it to the kinetic part of the classical statistical problem to see that it leads to $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ which is again a Gaussian (which according to the central limit theorem represents a random system, i.e. a maximum lack of information.)

Differences Between Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Both quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics appear to be statistical theories, but they also appear to be very different. Part of this is due to the different constraints which appear in each theory. For a classical statistical system, there are many particles which can undergo (or are constrained to undergo) two types of interactions. The first is a collision interaction between two particles which conserves momentum and kinetic energy. The second is the regular classical mechanical interaction with a potential which causes a particle to lose kinetic energy as it gains potential energy. If there is no potential $V(x)$, one might ask for $f(p,x)$, i.e. the probability to find a particle with momentum p at x . If there is no information about the system, then $f(p,x) = f(p)$ because there is no constraint restricting the particle to a specific region of space. The constraint represents information. If the momenta are random, then some people use the central limit theorem to argue that the distribution should be a Gaussian.

Boltzmann, however, used arguments about collisions. If a potential is introduced, collisions are still dominant and the momentum distribution exists in every region of space, but the physical density changes so that the force times the density at a point is balanced by the pressure on either side. If this were not the case, there would be flow and multiply particles would be undergoing collective motion, which would mean that they was some extra "information" in the system, or an extra constraint forcing them to move in a collective way.

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics is very different in that there seems to be a constraint imposed on a particle with momentum p . For example, a particle with momentum p in a box, will have a wavefunction of $\sin(px)$ (under certain conditions). The 2x2 matrix model [1] suggests that a particle is really undergoing zitterbewegung and so $\sin(px)$ is the consequence of this for a particle moving back and forth ($\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$). In other words, one does not have a point particle in quantum mechanics, but rather $f(p,x)$ which are unseparable. If a 2x2 matrix particle is placed in a potential, $V(x)$ will stir up many $f(p) \sin(px)$ terms (for the different momenta), but each carries its own $\sin(px)$ constraint, so given an $f(p)$, one immediately has a spatial distribution. Thus, for the quantum statistical distribution $W(x)$ containing more than one p to exist in the first place, there must be a potential. The potential plays an essential role in the quantum mechanical problem.

Let us consider the most "random" $f(p)$ distribution system for quantum mechanics. The central limit theorem suggests this would be $\exp(-p^2b)$ where b is constant. Calculating $W(x) = \sum_p f(p) \sin(px)$ yields $\exp(-cx^2)$ ($c = \text{constant}$) which is the ground state of the harmonic oscillator. This suggests that this one case, namely the ground state of a very specific potential, namely $.5 k x^2$,

has the greatest lack of information in quantum mechanics. Other potentials or higher oscillator states would have "more information". The question which arises is whether this "lack of information" in the quantum oscillator ground state is sufficient to apply to any spatial distribution in classical statistical mechanics. The answer might be no as the quantum system carries the $f(p)\sin(px)$ constraint which is not present in statistical mechanics. In statistical mechanics, a particle is a point which can be anywhere.

Interestingly, for the ground state of the quantum mechanical oscillator in the Schrodinger time independent equation, one can write:

$$[-E - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \text{del}^2] W(x) + V(x) W(x) = 0$$

Now $V(x) = .5kx^2$ and $W(x) = \exp(-ax^2)$ where a is a constant so:

$$V(x)W(x) = c \ln(d(x)) d(x) \text{ where } d(x) \text{ is the spatial density } W(x)W(x) \text{ and } c \text{ a constant.}$$

The term in square brackets multiplied by $W(x)$ is equivalent to $V(x) d(x)$. Dividing out $d(x)$ leads to:

$\ln(d(x) + c V(x)) = 0$ which looks like the variational result of:

$$d(x) \ln(d(x)) + c V(x) d(x)$$

which is Shannon's entropy approach to solving a statistical mechanical problem. Now, one might note that this is a spatial equation. One can, however, apply this form to the full statistical mechanical problem, namely:

$$f(p,x) \ln[f(p,x)] + b (p^2/2m + V(x)) f(p,x)$$

This will yield a Boltzmann distribution for momentum and an $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ distribution for space. Experiments show that this seems to apply to nature. Thus, one might argue that statistics contained in the quantum mechanical result with the least information lead to classical statistical mechanics.

Deterministic Classical Mechanics

Traditionally, quantum mechanics has been said to lead to classical mechanics in the large energy limit. Classical mechanics is deterministic, with a particle at a point x having a specific momentum at a specific time t . It is argued, however, that for low energies, a quantum 2×2 matrix model particle is of the form $\exp(ipx)$ where p , the momentum, is related to a wavelength. It is also argued that the particle is undergoing zitterbewegung in a region of space the size of the wavelength and so quantum theory is statistical at this level. Now, deterministic classical mechanics is "deterministic" based on the information brought back by the experiment. For example, one needs to measure p at each x at each t to see the deterministic behaviour and follow a particle in time. If one does not have this information, then one can assign a spatial probability distribution to a classical particle, say a particle on the spring. One would have a graph of $P(x) = dt = dx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the velocity at x . From this graph alone, one would not know if there were deterministic motion because the results could be averages and there could be a kind of random jumping about. Of course, the deterministic scenario is also a solution.

Conclusion

Examining the quantum mechanical time independent solution with the greatest lack of information (i.e. $f(p) = \exp(-ap^2)$ from the central limit theorem) where $W(x) = \sum_p f(p) \sin(px)$ ($W(x)$ being the wavefunction) yields a specific $W(x)$. This particular $W(x)$ with the greatest lack of information applies to the ground state of an oscillator. For this case, the time independent Schrodinger equation has the form: $\ln(d(x)) + b V(x) = 0$ where $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$ which is the variational result of: $d(x) \ln(d(x)) + V(x) d(x)$.

If one tries to apply this to classical statistical mechanics, it seems to give the full Boltzmann distribution $\exp[-(p^2/2m+V(x))/T]$, leading to the idea that statistical nature of the quantum solution with the greatest lack of information can describe classical statistical mechanics.

References

- [1] Francesco R. Ruggeri 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation. Zenodo 2018.
- [2] Francesco R. Ruggeri $\ln W$ As a Partition Function. Zenodo Sept. 2018;
- [3] U. Klein. The Statistical Origins of Quantum Mechanics. Physics Research International Volume 2010, Article ID 808424, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2010/808424>
- [4] Francesco R. Ruggeri Is Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity? Zenodo 2018.